

PROBLEM-SOLVING STYLES, WORK ATTITUDE, AND MOTIVATION OF SCHOOL HEADS IN RELATION TO WORK PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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Problem-Solving Styles, Work Attitude, and Motivation of School Heads in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

This study entitled “Problem-Solving Styles, Work Attitude, and Motivation of School Heads in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Intervention” was to examine the level of problem-solving styles, work attitude, and motivation on the work performance of the school heads. A Survey Questionnaire for Problem-Solving Styles, Work Attitude, and Motivation was administered to 105 respondents, who were the school heads from the Division of Talisay City and the Division of Bacolod City. Their Office Performance Commitment and Review Form was the basis for their work performance. To know the level of problem-solving styles and motivation, the mean was used and interpreted as very high, high, average, low, and very low. To know the level of work attitude, the mean was interpreted as very positive, positive, moderate, negative, and very negative. With the use of Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney, the results of this study revealed a significant difference in the problem-solving styles of school heads in terms of age, gender, and length of service. Using Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney, the findings showed no significant difference in the work attitude of the school heads regarding age, gender, and length of service. Based on the results, it was found that there was a significant difference in the motivation level of school heads in terms of age. Meanwhile, there was no significant difference in the motivation level regarding gender and length of service. Finally, using gamma, there was no significant relationship between the school heads’ problem-solving styles, work attitude, and motivation toward their work performance.

Keywords: *problem solving, work attitude, motivation, work performance*

Introduction

School heads are educational leaders of their schools, playing significant roles in administrative functions (Iremeka et. al., 2022). They are the core of the institutions and the success of which is partly based on their performances.

Each principal has their unique qualities – their leadership level, problem-solving, work attitudes, personalities, principles, and characters. These individualities then allow them to have different approaches and strategies when dealing with school concerns as well as taking the weight of official responsibilities required of them. Every principal in their position strives to actualize excellent administration as part of their work (Saraki, 2020).

The majority of school school heads have demonstrated ineffectiveness in carrying out their legally mandated duties, which is a drawback. The majority of school heads are ineffective, as demonstrated by Odogwu (2020), who found that a higher percentage of school heads lack an understanding of administrative principles, which lowers their productivity. Furthermore, the majority of school heads at public secondary schools are victims of inadequate approaches to problem-solving and work attitudes.

Having diverse problem-solving abilities is important for individuals to engage in a logical and realistic life. These skills are necessary in the workplace to provide solutions to ongoing challenges that predominantly impact educational outcomes. A range of competencies is crucial for professionals both in their careers and personal lives.

In his remarkable achievement, “Psychological Types,” Carl Jung introduced four fundamental functions in problem-solving around 1913 which are Thinking (T), Feeling (F), Sensing/Sensation (S), and Intuition (N). He believed that the four functions control the way people view and act in the world (Drenth, 2023). Furthermore, attitude is a powerful tool that shapes our mindset. It refers to a set of beliefs that help us evaluate people, situations, objects, or issues. Attitude significantly influences one’s behavior and actions toward people and how one performs their specific responsibilities (Iremeka, 2022).

Therefore, there is a need for the investigation of school heads’ problem-solving styles and work attitudes in the Division of Bacolod City. This study will investigate ways school heads’ problem-solving styles, work attitude, and motivation can lead to effective work performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain the problem-solving, attitudes, and motivation of school heads in the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City regarding their work performance, with the possibility of implementing interventions if deemed necessary. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of school heads in terms of age, sex, and length of service?
2. What is the extent of the problem-solving styles of school heads in the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City?

3. What is the level of work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City?
4. What is the level of motivation of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City?
5. What is the work performance of school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City as a whole and in terms of profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City in terms of their profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in the motivation level of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City in terms of their profile?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the level of work attitude and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City?
10. What intervention can be developed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to assess the work performance of principals in the Division of Bacolod City as influenced by their problem-solving styles and work attitudes. Thus, the researcher used a descriptive-correlational research design.

Descriptive-correlational research is a type of research design that aims to explore the relationship between two or more variables without asserting any cause-and-effect connection. It involves gathering and analyzing data on at least two variables to determine if there is a correlation between them (Aprecia, et. al., 2022). Furthermore, this type of research design describes the variables and measures the extent of the relationships between and among the variables. In this study, the problem-solving styles, work attitudes, and work performance of school heads were described, and their relationships were assessed.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 105 school heads from the seven (7) districts of the Division of Bacolod City and school heads from the Division of Talisay City. There was a total of 75 respondents from the Division of Bacolod and 30 respondents from the Division of Talisay City. During the time of the study, the respondents were the current school administrators of the mentioned divisions for the School Year 2023-2024.

Total population sampling, a type of purposive sampling, was employed in this research. Purposive sampling is used in research studies to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis. This method is appropriate when the researcher has a clear idea of the characteristics they want to study and aims to select a sample that is representative of those characteristics (Heath, 2023). Thus, all 75 principals from the seven (7) districts of the Division of Bacolod City were the respondents. Also, 23 elementary school heads and 7 secondary school heads were the respondents from the Division of Talisay City.

Instrument

The data-gathering instrument used to obtain this study was the Problem-Solving Style Questionnaire (PSSQ) which is a self-report questionnaire that measures four dimensions of problem-solving styles style: sensing, intuitive, feeling, and thinking. It was adapted from the study of Khan, M. J., Younas, T., & Ashraf, S. (2018). The researcher also used the Work Attitude of Principals Questionnaire from the study of Iremeka, F., et. al. (2022). The Motivation Questionnaire was taken from University Counseling and Consulting Services, University of Minnesota, Quick-Scoring Achievement Motivation Quiz (2020).

In determining the problem-solving styles of the school heads, there was a 20-item questionnaire upon which each statement was rated as 5 – Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Moderately Agree, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly Disagree. In determining their work attitude, a 12-item questionnaire was rated as 5 – Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Moderately Agree, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly Disagree.

In determining the motivation of the school heads, there was a 15-item questionnaire upon which each statement was rated as 5 – Very Often, 4 – Often, 3 – Sometimes, 2 – Rarely, and 1 – Not at All.

The instrument for work performance was the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF), a Department of Education assessment tool used to rate principals' yearly accomplishments.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City. After being approved, the researcher sought permission from the respondents to conduct a survey.

After obtaining the approval, the researcher personally distributed the survey forms to the respondents who were the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City school heads for School Year 2023-2024. The survey forms were then collected immediately

by the researcher to secure the confidentiality of information after giving enough time for the respondents of the study to accomplish it.

Data Analysis

After the data were gathered, the researcher tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

In the analyses and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used:

To answer the statement of the problem no. 1 which states, what is the profile of school heads in terms of age, sex, and length of service, frequency, and percent distribution were used.

To answer the statement of the problem no. 2 which states, what is the extent of the problem-solving styles of school heads in the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City, the mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 3 which states, what is the level of work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 4 which states, what is the level of motivation of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City, the mean was used.

To answer the statement of the problem no. 5 which states, what is the work performance of school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City as a whole and in terms of profile, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 6 which states, is there a significant difference between the work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City in terms of their profile, Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney were used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 7 which states, is there a significant difference between the motivation level of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City in terms of their profile, Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney were used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 8 which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of work attitude and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City, Gamma Coefficient was used.

To answer the statement of the problem no. 9 which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of motivation and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City, Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analyses, and interpretation of data gathered for this study.

Profile of School Heads

The table below shows the profile of school heads in the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	21-30 years old	0	0
	31-40 years old	4	3.8
	41-50 years old	28	26.7
	51 and above	73	69.5
	Total	105	100
Gender	Male	25	23.8
	Female	80	76.2
	Total	105	100
Length of Service	10 years below	7	6.7
	11 years above	98	93.3
	Total	105	100

The table presents that out of 105 school heads, 4 or 3.8 percent are aged 31-40 years old, 28 or 26.7 percent 41-50 years old, and 73 or 69.5 percent 51 and above. When it comes to sex, there were 25 or 23.8 percent male school heads and there were 80 or 76.2 percent female school heads. In length of service, there were 7 or 6.7 percent rendered 10 years of service and 98 or 93.3 percent served 11 years and above.

This shows that out of 105 participants, more school heads were aged 51 and above. There were also more female school heads and

most of them had been in the service for more than 11 years already.

Problem-Solving Styles of School Heads

The table below shows the problem-solving styles of the school heads in the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City.

Table 2. *Problem-Solving Styles of the School Heads in the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City*

<i>Problem-solving styles</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	55		
High	38		
Moderate	12	4.16	High
Low	0		
Very Low	0		
Total	105		

Based on the table above, 55 of the 105 school heads have a very high level of problem-solving styles, 38 have a high level of problem-solving styles, and 12 have a moderate level of problem-solving styles. In general, the school heads have high problem-solving styles with a mean of 4.16.

This shows that half of the respondents have very high problem-solving styles which they are using in their scope of work in the Department of Education.

Organizations need effective decision-making and problem-solving styles processes to manage a complex global environment (Galate, 2023). According to Avcı and Ayyıldız (2020), leadership and those who implement it play a critical role in the effectiveness of management and its processes. The concepts of leadership and leadership have been examined the most throughout history. This is because we are constantly confronted with these two ideas in every aspect of life.

Galate (2023) asserts that a leader is someone who exemplifies positive behavior for the community through mannerisms, values, and behavior patterns. To those beneath him or her, the leader sets an example of assimilation. The idea of leadership in the context of education is becoming increasingly popular as expectations for change and development in educational organizations grow.

Work Attitude Level of School Heads

The table below shows the work attitude level of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City.

Table 3. *Work Attitude Level of the School Heads in the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City*

<i>Level of Work Attitude</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very Positive	66		
Positive	34		
Moderate	5	4.39	Very Positive
Negative	0		
Very Negative	0		
Total	105		

Table 3 reveals that in terms of work attitude, 66 or most of the school heads possessed a very positive work attitude. 34 of them have a positive work attitude, and 5 school heads have a moderate work attitude. Generally, school heads have a very positive work attitude with a mean of 4.39.

This shows that the work attitude level of the school heads from the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City is high, thus manifesting a school leader who understands their job responsibilities and consistently maintains high-performance standards.

The results are in agreement with the study of Hermogeno & Dulos (2022) where they identified that school heads' behavior at work is often influenced by their feelings towards their profession. Thus, comprehending their work attitudes is crucial in understanding their conduct. School heads may have different work attitudes towards management and supervision, which are shaped by various factors such as their colleagues, the children, the school environment, their value system, and views about life. These factors interweave with positive or negative work attitudes towards their schools, the profession, educational activities, and the administration. A principal who demonstrates a professional work attitude understands their job responsibilities and consistently maintains high performance standards. Therefore, school heads' work attitudes are essential in enhancing the educational process (Hermogeno & Dulos, 2022).

Motivation Level of School Heads

The table on the next page shows the level of motivation of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City.

Table 4. *Motivation Level of the School Heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City*

<i>Level of Motivation</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	51		
High	43		
Moderate	11	4.2	High
Low	0		
Very Low	0		
Total	105		

Based on Table 4 above, 51 out of 105 respondents obtained a very high motivation level, 43 obtained a high motivation level, and 11 got a moderate motivation level. Generally, the school heads are highly motivated as shown by a mean of 4.2.

Thus, the school heads of the Divisions of Bacolod City and Talisay City have high motivation and therefore present that these school heads are motivated to do their tasks and responsibilities in their respective schools.

School heads play a crucial role in assisting instructors in enhancing their performance in a dynamic and adaptable organization like education (Sukandar, 2018). As a professional education leader in the school system, the principal's abilities and judgment are crucial in managing all organizational resources and collaborating with teachers to accomplish learning objectives. The principal is one aspect of education that influences teacher performance (Sukandar, 2018).

Work Performance as a whole and in terms of the Profile of School Heads

The table below shows the work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City as a whole and in terms of their profile.

Table 5. *Work Performance of School Heads in Terms of Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Age	21-30 years old	0	0	-
	31-40 years old	4	4.67	Outstanding
	41-50 years old	28	4.79	Outstanding
	51 and above	73	4.82	Outstanding
Gender	Male	25	4.75	Outstanding
	Female	80	4.83	Outstanding
Length of Service	10 years below	7	4.79	Outstanding
	11 years above	98	4.81	Outstanding

The table shows that out of 105 school heads, 4 or 4.67 percent are aged 31-40, 28 or 4.79 percent are aged 41-50, and 73 or 4.82 percent are aged 51 or above, all of whom obtained an outstanding work performance. In terms of gender, there were 25 or 4.75 percent were males and 80 or 4.83 percent were females, all obtained an outstanding work performance. Meanwhile, in terms of length of service, 7 or 4.79 percent of the respondents have rendered service 10 years below, and 98 or 4.81 percent of the respondents have served for 11 years above, all obtained outstanding work performance results.

The school heads of the two divisions under study showed outstanding work performance regardless of their demographic profile, such as age, gender, and length of service, which is a good indication that they can perform their duties and responsibilities well without having possible hindering factors like age, gender, and length of service.

The data is connected to the study of Ikechukwu (2018) which identified that the role of a school principal is to manage and administer the human and material resources required for the operation of secondary schools. This involves handling the managerial and administrative responsibilities of the school, including organizing, supervising, directing, and mobilizing both material and human resources to achieve the school's goals and objectives.

School administration refers to the direction and organization of personnel toward accomplishing a specific goal (Ikechukwu, 2018). Effective school administration involves properly organizing and directing both human and material resources to achieve the school's goals and objectives. It is the art of ensuring that personnel's daily needs are met, creating a safe environment, and providing the necessary health support (Paget,

2019).

Difference in Work Attitude when grouped in terms of Age

The table below shows the difference in the work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of age.

Table 6. *Difference in Work Attitude of School Heads when grouped in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
31-40 years old	4	60.00
41-50 years old	28	59.07
51 and above	73	50.29

Computed Value (H): 1.91
P-Value: 0.384
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean work of attitude of 4 school heads aged 31-40 years old was 60.00, the mean work of attitude of 28 school heads aged 41-50 years old was 59.07, and the mean work of attitude of 73 school heads aged 51 above years old was 50.29.

Upon using Kruskal, a computed value of 1.91 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is a significant difference between the work attitude and age of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City.

According to Lumby (2019), there is no discernible variation in the work performance of younger and older teachers, suggesting that there are no major age-related disparities in the motivational tactics used by their leaders.

It has been noted that senior employees have more positive sentiments about their occupations than do younger employees. But according to Barnes-Farrel and Matthews (2018), this is an oversimplified perspective of the roles that aging and age play in the emergence of positive work attitudes and engagement.

Difference in Work Attitude when grouped In terms of Gender

The table next page shows the difference in the work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of gender.

Table 7. *Difference in Work Attitude of School Heads when grouped in terms of Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	25	51.3
Female	80	53.53

Computed Value (U): 957.50
P-Value: 0.748
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean work of attitude of 25 male school heads was 51.3 and the mean work of attitude of 80 female school heads was 53.53.

Upon using Mann Whitney, a computed value of 957.50 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is no significant difference in the work attitude of the schools' heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when it comes to gender.

The gender of the school heads does not significantly create variations in their work attitude as educational leaders in each of their institutions.

The World Values Survey inquiries about a person's views on the proper roles that men and women should play in society, as well as the significance of labor in one's life (Campa & Serafinelli, 2019). The results are consistent with the research of Fujimoto (2018), which showed that attitudes about labor are not entirely determined by differences in gender. Also, according to a study by Wanakacha (2019), female school heads are more driven to carry out their responsibilities than the male.

Difference in Work Attitude when grouped In terms of Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the work attitude of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of length of service.

Table 8. *Difference in Work Attitude of School Heads when grouped in terms of Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
10 years below	7	65.57
11 years above	98	52.1

Computed Value (U): 255.00
P-Value: 0.257
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean work of attitude of 7 school heads in the length of service 10 years below was 65.57, and the mean work of attitude of 98 school heads in the length of service 11 years above was 52.1.

Using Mann Whitney, a computed value of 255.00 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the work attitude and length of service of the school heads from the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City.

The work attitude of school heads do not necessarily vary based on the number of years they have rendered in the institution.

The success or failure of any organization is determined on the abilities, aptitudes, and dispositions of its workforce. The achievement of an organization's goals is measured in terms of revenue or status progress. As a result, when workers perform poorly, the organization's production declines. The participants' work attitudes and length of service were shown to be significantly correlated (Codilla, 2019).

Based on Codilla's (2019) findings, it can be inferred that an employee's length of service has an impact on their work attitude. Therefore, it is advised that office staff members pursue higher education and that management offer them opportunities for academic growth. It is also advised that more research be done to investigate participants' work attitudes in addition to their performance, including production and punctuality.

Difference in Motivation Level when grouped in terms of Age

The table below shows the difference in the motivation of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and the Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of age.

Table 9. *Difference in Motivation Level of School Heads when grouped in terms of Age*

Age	f	Mean Rank
31-40 years old	4	56.25
41-50 years old	28	41.36
51 and above	73	57.29

Computed Value (H): 6.85

P-Value: 0.033

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean level of motivation of 4 school heads aged 31-40 years old was 56.25, the mean level of motivation of 28 school heads aged 41-50 years old was 41.36, and the mean level of motivation of 73 school heads aged 51 above years old was 57.29.

Using Kruskal, a computed value of 6.85 was obtained which is higher than the P-value which is 0.033 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between the motivation level and age of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City. Therefore, the age of the school heads affects their motivation level, especially when it comes to their responsibilities and duties as school administrators.

This is correlated to Nyamubi (2018) which stated that as school heads age, they become accustomed to their work environments and the profession, which makes them content and motivates them to give their schools their all. This study brought to light the new finding that younger school heads put in more effort to enhance their job performance in order to properly carry out their duties. There are more young school heads in compared to older ones, they are in fewer secondary schools, but it is easier for them to get a job elsewhere. According to Sukandar (2018), younger school heads are thought to be more innovative, easier to train, and in better physical shape than more experienced educational leaders.

Difference in Motivation Level when grouped In terms of Gender

The table shows the difference in the motivation level of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of gender.

Table 10. *Difference in Motivation Level of School Heads when grouped in terms of Gender*

Gender	f	Mean Rank
Male	25	43.16
Female	80	56.08

Computed Value (U): 754.00

P-Value: 0.064

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean level of motivation of 25 male school heads was 43.16, and the mean level of motivation of 80 female school heads was 56.08.

Using Mann Whitney, a computed value of 754.00 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is no significant difference between the level of motivation and gender of the school heads from the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City. Therefore, the school heads' motivation level does not necessarily vary when it comes to their gender.

Hermogeno & Dulos' (2022) study investigated the potential impact of school heads' gender on their motivation and job satisfaction. The study discovered that female educational leaders in Danish schools showed greater levels of empathy and job satisfaction as well as self-efficacy compared to their male counterparts. Meador (2019) investigated the gender differences in learning outcomes as well as the contribution of school heads' gender to the reduction of learning disparity.

Difference in Motivation Level when grouped in terms of Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the motivation of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City when grouped in terms of length of service.

Table 11. *Difference in Motivation Level of School Heads when grouped in terms of Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
10 years below	7	46.71
11 years above	98	53.45

Computed Value (U): 299.00
P-Value: 0.571
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

The table shows that the mean level of motivation of 7 school heads in the length of service 10 years below was 46.71, and the mean level of motivation of 98 school heads in the length of service 11 years above was 53.45.

Using Kruskal, a computed value of 299.00 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is no significant difference between the level of motivation and length of service of school heads from the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City. Therefore, the data show that the years school heads spend in their institutions do not affect their motivation level.

School heads are important human resources because they greatly enhance the school's effectiveness and efficiency. Sound leadership is essential for an effective school and is a key factor in determining the institution's competitiveness (Siraj, 2018).

The results are consistent with the study by Codilla (2019), which indicated a substantial correlation between the participants' motivation and service duration. Based on Codilla's (2019) findings, it can be inferred that the length of service has an impact on school heads' motivation. Therefore, it is advised that office staff members pursue higher education, and that management offer them with opportunities for academic growth.

Relationship between Work Attitude And Work Performance of School Heads

The table next page shows the relationship between the work attitude and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City.

Table 12. *Relationship between Work Attitude and Work Performance of the School Heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City*

<i>Level of Work Attitude</i>	<i>Level of Work Performance</i>					<i>Total</i>
	<i>Outstanding</i>	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	<i>Satisfactory</i>	<i>Unsatisfactory</i>	<i>Poor</i>	
Very Positive	65	1	0	0	0	66
Positive	34	0	0	0	0	34
Neutral	5	0	0	0	0	5
Negative	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Negative	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	104	1	0	0	0	105

Computed Value (G): -1.00
P-Value: 0.314
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

Table 12 reveals that most of the respondents have a very positive level of work performance in relation to their work attitude: 66 out of 105, 34 of the respondents obtained positive, and 5 of the respondents obtained neutral.

Upon using Gamma, a computed value of -1.00 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is no significant relationship between the level of work performance and work attitude of the school heads from

the Division of Bacolod City and Talisay City. Therefore, the school heads' work attitude does not affect their work performance.

This is in connection with the study of Cabrera and Estacio (2022), that a person's work performance is determined by their work attitude and the way they perceive the world. School head attitudes toward certain jobs, goods or services, coworkers, management, or the business as a whole can be either favorable or negative at work. Workdays are more fun when people have positive attitudes.

Tasks are completed without complaint and at a better standard. They found out that every aspect linked to attitude has a beneficial impact on worker performance. The performance of school heads is significantly impacted by their motivation and commitment to their jobs.

Relationship between Motivation Level and Work Performance of School Heads

The table below shows the relationship between the motivation level and work performance of the school heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City.

Table 13. Relationship between Motivation Level and Work Performance of the School Heads of the Division of Bacolod City and Division of Talisay City

Level of Motivation	Level of Work Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Poor	
Very High	50	1	0	0	0	51
High	43	0	0	0	0	43
Moderate	11	0	0	0	0	11
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	104	1	0	0	0	105

Computed Value (G): -1.00

P-Value: 0.313

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at .05 level of significance

Table 13 reveals that most of the respondents have a very high level of work performance in relation to their motivational level with 51 out of 105, 43 of the respondents obtained high, and 11 of the respondents obtained moderate.

Upon using Gamma, a computed value of -1.00 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the motivation level and work performance of the school heads of the Divisions of Bacolod City and Talisay City. Therefore, the school heads' motivation level and work performance do not necessarily relate to each other.

In connection, motivation is a key component of a meaningful concept. Numerous studies have examined the relationship between performance in various institutions, motivation, and its component elements (Reizer, Brender-Ilan & Sheaffer, 2019).

Additionally, the performance of school heads is significantly impacted by their motivation and commitment to their jobs (Cabrera & Estacio, 2022). Motivation is important because, without it, even those with the necessary information, skills, and abilities cannot put in the time and effort necessary to complete their work.

Furthermore, school heads concentrate on inspiring motivation by being enthusiastic and upbeat, involving instructors in imagining a desirable future state, setting clear expectations, and exhibiting dedication to the school's objectives (Siraj, 2018). Additionally, research indicates that the more experienced educational leaders are, the more attention they devote to their work, and as a result, the greater the likelihood that they will remain with their school (Reizer, Brender-Ilan & Sheaffer, 2019). Teachers with strong aspirations to meet school objectives would thus make plans to remain at the school and improve their teaching due to the motivating and inspiring leadership they get.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings of this research study, the conclusions that were arrived are as follows:

There were more school heads aged 51 and above, more female school heads, and more school heads who have been in the service for more than 11 years.

The problem-solving styles of school heads from the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City is high.

The school heads of the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City have very positive work attitude.

The school heads of the Division of Bacolod and Division of Talisay City have high motivation level.

The work performance of school heads from the Divisions of Bacolod and Talisay City in terms of age, gender, and length of service is outstanding.

The problem-solving styles of school heads is influenced by their age, gender, and length of service.

The work attitude of school heads is not affected by their age, gender, and length of service.

The motivation level of school heads is influenced by their age while their gender and length of service does not necessarily affect their motivation.

The problem-solving styles and work performance level of school heads do not affect each other.

The work attitude of school heads do not influence their work performance.

The motivation level and work performance of school heads does not influence each other.

With reference to the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

It is recommended that a mentorship program be implemented to leverage the experience of older and more seasoned school heads where they can guide newer school administrators.

Provide school heads with professional development opportunities focusing on motivation, work attitude, and problem-solving to strengthen their roles further.

Create platforms and opportunities for school leaders to share their best practices and innovative solutions to common challenges.

Foster a positive work environment by encouraging work-life balance, implementing recognition programs, and organizing team-building activities. Additionally, it offers resources for stress management and professional counseling to uphold a positive work attitude.

Provide training and development opportunities tailored to the needs of school heads at different career stages and cater to different age groups, genders, and length of service.

Promote a culture of inclusivity and respect where school heads, regardless of age, gender, or length of service, feel valued.

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